

ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY IN NEWBORNS

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Infectious pathology remains one of the most pressing issues in neonatology. Infectious diseases in newborns are intrauterine and acquired after birth (postnatal). Postnatal infections can occur both on an outpatient basis and nosocomial. The latter are also called hospital or nosocomial infections. According to the World Health Organization, in the structure of causes of neonatal death, severe infections account for more than 36%. It should be noted that infectious pathology of the perinatal period in the structure of morbidity and infant mortality in recent years ranks third in frequency after hypoxia/asphyxia during childbirth and congenital anomalies. A twofold increase in the incidence of sepsis compared to previous years (from 2.8 to 4.4 per 10,000 live births) is noteworthy. In addition, there is an increase in the frequency of intrauterine infections, which largely determine the level of stillbirth and early neonatal mortality, the frequency of which has also doubled over the past 5 years [1, 2].

Infectious diseases are the leading cause of neonatal hospitalization. The frequency of infectious and inflammatory diseases among full-term newborns hospitalized in a hospital has not changed over the past 10 years and averages 50% [2, 3].

Infectious agents can cause diseases such as sepsis, pneumonia, tracheobronchitis, meningitis, necrotizing ulcerative enterocolitis, osteomyelitis, arthritis, pyoderma, omphalitis, rhinitis, conjunctivitis, otitis, etc. Entrance gates for infectious agents in newborns are the mucous membranes of the respiratory tract, digestive system, eyes, urethra, damaged areas of the skin, catheterized veins, umbilical wound, external auditory canal.

Etiology. The causative agents of infectious diseases in newborns can be bacteria, viruses, chlamydia, mycoplasmas, fungi, protozoa. The etiological structure of infectious diseases, depending on the time (intrauterine or postnatal) and the place of occurrence (outpatient or nosocomial), is somewhat different. So, among the causative agents of intrauterine infections, the most common are viral (herpesvirus infections), mycoplasma, chlamydial infections, among bacterial pathogens - Escherichia coli and other enterobacteria, group B streptococci, listeria, citrobacter, bacteroids, toxoplasma, etc. [4, 5].

The causative agents of postnatal infection can be the child's own microflora or any hospital microorganisms in the case of a child's stay in the hospital for 72 hours or more. With the development of an infection on an outpatient basis, pathogens such as *E. coli* and other members of the Enterobacteriaceae, *S. aureus*, *H. influenzae*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* families are mainly sown. Unlike hospital infections, outpatient infections have a more favorable course and outcome, and the spectrum of antibacterial sensitivity of pathogens is wide enough, which usually does not cause difficulties in choosing antibiotic therapy. At home, in the absence of contact with sources of hospital strains, secondary infection rarely occurs.

In recent years, there has been a global trend towards an increase in the proportion of purulent-septic diseases in newborns caused by gram-negative opportunistic microorganisms belonging mainly to the Enterobacteriaceae and Pseudomonaceae families. There is a change in the proportion of certain types of microorganisms. Thus, the proportion of staphylococci decreased from 65.3 to 4.9%, while the proportion of enterobacteria increased from 25 to 59.3%, and pseudomonads - from 9 to 29.3%. Comparative analysis of the results of our studies conducted in 1995–1998 and 2003–2005 on the study of the microflora of the respiratory tract in newborns with ventilator-associated pneumonia revealed that in previous years Gram-negative bacteria, and, above all, *Ps. aeruginosa*, whose role has increased in recent years. *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* began to act as a cause of nosocomial pneumonia much more often (14% compared to 2.6% in previous years). The role of such microorganisms as *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Erwinia amilovora*, *Plesiomonas shigelloides*, *Citrobacter diversus*, which almost never occurred in previous years, has increased.

The choice of antibacterial drug Effective treatment of infection in newborns is based on complex therapy, including three approaches: 1) etiotropic treatment aimed at eradicating pathogens; 2) pathogenetic treatment, designed to break the vicious circle of pathogenetic mechanisms of formation and maintenance of inflammatory processes; 3) symptomatic treatment, leading to a decrease in the severity of clinical manifestations of infection and complications, which allows you to gain time during which etiotropic and pathogenetic treatment will ultimately provide recovery.

Antibacterial therapy of infectious and inflammatory diseases in newborns should be supplemented by methods of pathogenetic and symptomatic treatment. A mandatory addition to antibiotics in the treatment of severe forms

of diseases is substitution therapy with intravenous immunoglobulin preparations. Intensive antibiotic therapy should be combined with the prevention of fungal superinfection by using antifungal drugs (nystatin, diflucan, etc.) from the 2nd week of treatment. For the prevention and treatment of intestinal dysbacteriosis, it is necessary to prescribe a course of probiotics (bifidumbacterin, acipol, linex) both during antibiotic therapy and after its cancellation. According to the indications, oxygen therapy is carried out, metabolic shifts are corrected, anemia and disorders of the cardiovascular, respiratory and nervous systems are treated. An important role in the treatment is played by ensuring the energy needs of the sick organism of the newborn, taking into account the caloric content of nutrition, if necessary, parenteral nutrition is used.

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